

Research on an Improper Fractional Integral

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Abstract: In this paper, based on Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we study an improper fractional integral. Moreover, our result is a generalization of traditional calculus result.

Keywords: Jumarie type of R-L fractional calculus, new multiplication, fractional analytic functions, improper fractional integral.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the applications of fractional calculus in various fields of science is growing rapidly, such as physics, biology, mechanics, electrical engineering, viscoelasticity, control theory, modelling, economics, etc [1-15]. However, the rule of fractional derivative is not unique, many scholars have given the definitions of fractional derivatives. The common definition is Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative. Other useful definitions include Caputo fractional derivative, Grunwald-Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivative, and Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative to avoid non-zero fractional derivative of constant function [16-20].

In this paper, based on Jumarie type of R-L fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we study the following improper fractional integral:

$$({}_0I_{+\infty}^{\alpha}) \left[(\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2} \otimes_{\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-2)} \right],$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. In fact, our result is a generalization of traditional calculus result.

II. PRELIMINARIES

Firstly, we introduce the fractional calculus used in this paper.

Definition 2.1 ([21]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. The Jumarie's modified Riemann-Liouville (R-L) α -fractional derivative is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^{\alpha})[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)-f(x_0)}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt, \quad (1)$$

And the Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville α -fractional integral is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}I_x^{\alpha})[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad (2)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function.

Proposition 2.2 ([22]): If α, β, x_0, C are real numbers and $\beta \geq \alpha > 0$, then

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^{\alpha})[(x-x_0)^{\beta}] = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta-\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{\beta-\alpha}, \quad (3)$$

and

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[C] = 0. \quad (4)$$

Definition 2.3 ([23]): If x, x_0 , and a_n are real numbers for all n , $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, that is, $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}$ on some open interval containing x_0 , then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic at x_0 . Furthermore, if $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is continuous on closed interval $[a, b]$ and it is α -fractional analytic at every point in open interval (a, b) , then f_α is called an α -fractional analytic function on $[a, b]$.

In the following, we introduce a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions.

Definition 2.4 ([24]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Assume that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional power series at $x = x_0$,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad (5)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \quad (6)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_m}{\Gamma(m\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{m\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Definition 2.5 ([25]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x is a real number. The α -fractional exponential function is defined by

$$E_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (9)$$

On the other hand, the α -fractional cosine and sine function are defined as follows:

$$\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{2n\alpha}}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2n}, \quad (10)$$

and

$$\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{(2n+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (2n+1)}. \quad (11)$$

Theorem 2.6 (integration by parts for fractional calculus) ([26]): Assume that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, a, b are real numbers, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are α -fractional analytic functions, then

$$({}_aI_b^\alpha) \left[f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha ({}_aD_x^\alpha) [g_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \right] = [f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha)]_{x=a}^{x=b} - ({}_aI_b^\alpha) \left[g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha ({}_aD_x^\alpha) [f_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \right]. \quad (12)$$

Theorem 2.7 ([27]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, then the improper α -fractional integral

$$({}_0I_{+\infty}^\alpha) \left[\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (-1)} \right] = \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (13)$$

III. MAIN RESULT

In this section, we solve a fractional integral involving fractional trigonometric function.

Theorem 3.1: Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, then the improper α -fractional integral

$$({}_0I_{+\infty}^{\alpha}) \left[(\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2} \otimes_{\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-2)} \right] = \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (14)$$

Proof

$$\begin{aligned} &({}_0I_{+\infty}^{\alpha}) \left[(\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2} \otimes_{\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-2)} \right] \\ &= ({}_0I_{+\infty}^{\alpha}) \left[(\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2} \otimes_{\alpha} ({}_0D_x^{\alpha}) \left(- \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \right) \right] \\ &= \left[(\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2} \otimes_{\alpha} \left(- \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \right) \right]_{x=0}^{x=+\infty} \\ &\quad - ({}_0I_{+\infty}^{\alpha}) \left[\left(- \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \right) \otimes_{\alpha} ({}_0D_x^{\alpha}) \left[(\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2} \right] \right] \\ &\quad \text{(by integration by parts for fractional calculus)} \\ &= 0 - 0 + ({}_0I_{+\infty}^{\alpha}) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \otimes_{\alpha} 2 \cdot \sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) \right] \\ &= ({}_0I_{+\infty}^{\alpha}) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \otimes_{\alpha} \sin_{\alpha}(2x^{\alpha}) \right] \\ &= ({}_0I_{+\infty}^{\alpha}) \left[\left(2 \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \otimes_{\alpha} \sin_{\alpha}(2x^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} ({}_0D_x^{\alpha}) \left[2 \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right) \right] \right] \\ &= ({}_0I_{+\infty}^{\alpha}) \left[\sin_{\alpha}(t^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-1)} \right] \\ &= \frac{\pi}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad \text{Q.e.d.}$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on Jumarie's modified R-L fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we solve an improper fractional integral. In addition, our result is a generalization of ordinary calculus result. In the future, we will continue to use Jumarie type of R-L fractional calculus and the new multiplication of fractional analytic functions to solve problems in engineering mathematics and fractional differential equations.

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